

IPBES AR BBA Chapter 2 – Snowball literature search for literature on business dependency on biodiversity (R2)

Number of subsampled papers identifying various measurements of dependencies

Ecosystem service	Number of papers reviewed
Pollination services	38
Freshwater quantity	16
Food and feed	1
Physical and psychological experiences	1
Regulation of climate	1
Regulation of organisms detrimental to humans	2
Regulation of freshwater and coastal water quality	1
Medicinal, biochemical and genetic resources	1
Materials and assistance	1
Formation, protection and decontamination of soils	2
Habitat creation and maintenance	2